

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SERVER-SIDE RENDERING AND CLIENT-SIDE RENDERING IN FRONTEND WEB APPLICATIONS

Sidorov Denys

Specialist degree

Odessa I.I. Mechnikov National University

Abstract

This article presents a comparative analysis of server-side rendering (SSR) and client-side rendering (CSR). It examines the impact of rendering methods on performance and user experience (UX). The main advantages and principles of each approach are discussed, including download speed, interactivity and SEO optimization. The importance of choosing an approach based on specific project requirements is addressed, as well as the possibilities of hybrid rendering as a means of combining the best features of both methods.

Keywords: server-side rendering (SSR), client-side rendering (CSR), frontend, performance, user experience (UX), interactivity, web applications.

Introduction

In web development, the choice of rendering approach plays an important role in shaping user experience (UX) and the performance of web applications. Server-side rendering (SSR) and client-side rendering (CSR) are two primary methods used to display content on web pages. Each has its own advantages and disadvantages, and understanding these aspects is essential for frontend developers aiming to create fast and responsive web applications.

The choice between SSR and CSR depends on numerous factors: the type of application, the target audience, and performance and UX requirements. For instance, for news websites or blogs where fast loading and SEO are paramount, SSR may be the optimal solution. Conversely, for complex web applications that require high interactivity and dynamic content updates, CSR often proves to be more suitable.

Understanding the differences between SSR and CSR will help developers make more informed decisions when designing web applications. In an environment of ever-increasing user demands for speed and

quality of online services, knowledge of the features of these technologies becomes a significant competitive advantage. The aim of this article is to conduct a comparative analysis of SSR and CSR, exploring their impact on performance and UX.

Main part. Types of rendering

In web development, rendering plays a central role in how users interact with web applications. Understanding the fundamental concepts of rendering allows frontend developers to make more informed decisions when creating interfaces, as well as to optimize performance and enhance UX. The two most common approaches – SSR and CSR – possess unique characteristics that influence the way content is displayed and interacted with by users.

The method in which HTML code for pages is generated on the server and sent to the client in a ready-to-use format is known as SSR. This means that all the content of the page is assembled before it is loaded by the user, significantly reducing loading times and improving user perception (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The principle of SSR

The process begins with the client sending a request to the server. The server processes this request, performs necessary operations such as accessing the database and handling business logic, and then creates the HTML page. This page is sent back to the client, who immediately sees the ready content [1]. Thus, the

user can start interacting with the application almost instantly, without having to wait for additional resources to load.

One of the main advantages of SSR is **improved search engine optimization**. Since all content is available immediately, search engine crawlers can more easily index the pages, positively affecting the site's visi-

bility in search engines. This can be **beneficial for users with slow internet connections**, as they receive a fully rendered page rather than relying on the loading and execution of JavaScript code on the client side. Thus, SSR is a powerful tool for creating web applications where loading speed and SEO optimization are important [2]. It finds wide application in various domains, from content sites to complex web applications where high-quality UX is required.

The approach in which HTML code and page content are generated directly on the client side using JavaScript is known as CSR. Instead of the server sending ready-made HTML, it provides a minimal template along with the necessary scripts, which the browser loads and executes to create the complete page (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The principle of CSR

In the CSR process, the basic HTML page and JavaScript files are loaded first. After this, the browser executes the scripts, which can fetch dynamic content through API requests. This allows for the creation of highly interactive single-page applications, where users can interact with the interface without the need for page reloads. For example, when navigating between sections of the application, the content updates asynchronously, making the interaction smoother and faster.

One of the main advantages of CSR is its **high interactivity and responsiveness of the interface**. Users can receive updates without delays, and frontend developers can leverage modern frameworks such as React, Angular, or Vue.js to create complex and dynamic applications [3]. Additionally, CSR **reduces the load on the server since much** of the processing occurs on the client side. It is a powerful tool for creating modern web applications where interactivity and UX are paramount. However, the choice between CSR and SSR depends on the specific requirements of the project and the target audience.

Analysis of the impact of rendering choice on performance and UX

In the world of web development, frontend performance and UX are critical factors for the success of any web application or site. In a highly competitive landscape, users expect instant access to information and

intuitive interaction with the interface. Therefore, frontend developers face the important task of optimizing their projects to ensure not only fast loading times but also positive UX.

The primary aspect of web development, along with the choice of rendering method, is UX. It encompasses all aspects of the user's interaction with the product, including usability, intuitiveness, and satisfaction. A good UX ensures ease of navigation, content accessibility, and a quick response of the interface to user actions [4]. It plays an important role in retaining users and increasing their loyalty to the product.

Performance, in the context of web development, refers to the speed and efficiency with which a web application or site loads and processes data. Important performance aspects include page load time, responsiveness to user actions, and overall application stability. High performance contributes to reduced waiting times, which in turn enhances user interaction efficiency with the site.

One of the important factors influencing these parameters is the choice of rendering method. Each approach has its own advantages and limitations that can significantly impact performance and UX (table 1).

Table 1

Comparative analysis of SSR and CSR [5, 6]

Parameter	SSR	CSR
Initial loading time and content	Fast, users see content immediately. Ready HTML content is sent right away.	Slower, time is needed to load JavaScript Content is loaded asynchronously after the initial load.
Interactivity	Limited, requires page reloads for updates.	High, users can interact without delays.
Server load	High under heavy traffic	Server load is lower after the initial load
SEO optimization	Excellent, search engines can index content.	There may be issues with indexing dynamic content.
Usability	Intuitive interaction, content is available immediately.	A «blank» screen may occur during the initial load.
Performance under load	May decrease under high server load.	More stable performance after the initial load.
Interface responsiveness	Depends on page load speed.	High responsiveness after the initial load.
User experience	High satisfaction level due to fast loading.	Can be high, but depends on application optimization.

The use of SSR is recommended in situations where a project requires high visibility in search engines. This approach makes it easier for search robots to index content, since pages are loaded in a ready-made HTML format. When content changes frequently and requires updating with each request, SSR ensures that users receive the most up-to-date information. An example of SSR usage is the **news portal CNN**, which enables users to see current news immediately without delays, which is crucial in an environment of constant information updates [7].

Another example is e-commerce sites like **Amazon**. Here, SSR provides fast loading of product pages, which is important for enhancing UX and increasing conversion rates. Quick loading of the initial page helps retain customers on the site, minimizing the likelihood of them leaving due to long wait times [8].

Using CSR is useful in situations where a project includes complex interactive elements. In applications where data is updated in real-time (such as messengers and social networks), CSR avoids page reloads and ensures instant interface updates. If the application requires complex authentication and authorization, CSR allows for more flexible management of user states.

An example of CSR usage is the social network **Facebook**, which allows users to instantly update their news feeds, comment, and interact with posts without needing to reload the page [9]. This creates a smooth and seamless experience that users appreciate.

Hybrid approaches combine the advantages of both methods, providing fast loading and interactivity. Using SSR for the initial load and CSR for further navigation allows for better UX. For example, **LinkedIn** employs this approach to quickly load user profiles and news feeds while ensuring smooth interaction during navigation and engagement with content. Basic data is loaded on the server, speeding up page rendering, while interactive elements like messages and notifications are processed on the client side [10]. Overall, the choice of approach depends on the specifics of the project and user requirements. An optimal combination of methods can significantly improve both performance and UX.

Conclusion

A comparative analysis of SSR and CSR shows that both approaches have their unique advantages and disadvantages, which significantly impact performance and frontend UX. The use of SSR provides a fast-bootstrapping process and better SEO optimization, which is especially important for content-oriented sites. However, its limited interactivity may lead to less smooth interactions. On the other hand, CSR offers a high level of interactivity and dynamism, making it ideal for applications that require frequent real-time data updates. Nevertheless, it may encounter performance issues on slow connections or outdated devices.

The choice of approach should be based on the specific requirements of the project, target audience, and type of content. Successful implementation of rendering depends on developers' ability to adapt technologies to user needs, thereby creating a quality and responsive interface.

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